

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation: The article discusses the critical factors of effective management in the development of higher education, as well as the methods of implementing it in our country's universities using the corporate management system and foreign experience in abandoning the authoritarian and administrative-bureaucratic management model in the educational system.

Keywords: management, corporate governance, authoritarianism, administrative-bureaucratic management, accountability in management, voting in management.

In the world, the effort of each Higher Educational Institution to establish a particular model based on its features is becoming relevant on the basis of the general principles of the system of corporate governance. Based on this technique, American, British, Swedish, Finnish, and Japanese corporate governance models were developed and shown great efficiency. In this case, we can see that each state places a premium on the implementation of the national model of corporate governance approach in its educational system. " Management functions can be carried out in a variety of ways. As a result, the main criterion that determines the need to organize management, that is, management activities, is the goal set before a person or an institution, and the assignment of tasks to achieve it, the pre - planning of the activities to be organized, the choice of methods of implementation, the selection of executors based on the content and essence of the tasks, and the selection of executors based on the content and essence of the tasks.

The core meaning of the phrase "corporate governance" is "interactive communication between group members." It is said that in order to improve management effectiveness, it is necessary to establish an active dialogue among all participants, socialize the property by increasing the exposure of minor shareholders, i.e., to attract to the management of the enterprise everyone who is interested in its activities at this or that level. Among the center's primary areas of action are "the introduction of organizational forms and new methods of corporate governance, training and professional development of sphere employees in accordance with international requirements"[2]. If this tariff is applied in relation to the institution of higher education, it means attracting to the management of the institution of Higher Education any person who is interested in its activities at this or that level.

The International Conference "Values and Ethics in Higher Education," held in Washington in 2006, and the conference "Management Printing in Higher Education," conducted in 2007, focused on developing appropriate management models for the educational system and assuring its future effectiveness[3]. According to Khaled Zaman, a professor at Pakistan's University of Saradha, in his study titled "Effective Management and Quality Education in the World Higher Education System," it is not possible to create an effective management model in the world's higher education system, but independence and accountability in management itself will bring about quality.

In addition, regular study is conducted to investigate the benefits of the worldwide trend of management of the world's potential higher education institutions and to develop ideal management. By the twenty-first century, the corporate governance model had been tried in practice in developed universities around the world and had been ranked as the most effective system as a consequence of its bleaching over time. However, there is a need to adjust the corporate governance system's principles, internal structure, and regulations to social developments, Times demand, and to synchronize the Democratic prints of each state. As a result, various studies are being conducted in the world's developed

universities and research centers in order to create innovative models of educational institution management and change current ones. "It is essential that managers and employees in educational institutions have the necessary knowledge, skills, and abilities to master the functional aspects of management, achieve labor productivity, approach work responsibly, steer the team toward the goal, adapt educational institution management to internal and external changes, and evolve new innovations." Therefore, it is required, first of all, to cultivate the outlook, knowledge, attitude to the Times and the plane of creativity of managers and professors and teachers working in the higher education system.

In recent years, significant emphasis has been placed on upgrading the spheres' "administration procedures." The head of our state mentioned this and emphasized that radical changes in the techniques and approaches in the corporate governance system have made a significant contribution to ensuring its compliance with real market relations and renunciation of conservative views, but at a time when it was discovered that the organization of the Joint-Stock Companies and the management of the business. It was stated that "the corporate method is an important condition for the transition to a market economy, the vital necessity of studying the experience of developed countries in this regard, particularly issues of modern management with a thorough knowledge of the field, as well as the involvement of young specialists who are able to apply marketing methods in practice"[6]. As a result, the need to prepare and bring higher education to both capitalist relations and market economic rules arose. It is also necessary to renounce the conservative viewpoint, authoritarian and administrative-bureaucratic management style by bringing corporate governance principles into Higher Education management.

In conclusion, the implementation of corporate governance principles in higher education institutions results in a significant shift in the educational system. Governance is the formation of openness, transparency, legitimacy, and public control, which will assure higher education progress. The experience of

industrialized countries arises from the fact that corporate governance is a market and a modern need.

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